

Factors Associated with Choice of Birth Attendants in the Working Area of Batipuh I Primary Health Care, Tanah Datar District West Sumatera

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ABSTRACT

Background: The aim of the study was determine factors associated with choice of birth attendants in the working area of Batipuh I Primary Health Care, Tanah Datar District West Sumatera Province Indonesia.

Methods: The study was conducted using a cross sectional study, in the working area of Batipuh I Primary Health Care, Tanah Datar District West Sumatera Province Indonesia from January-March 2019. The population in this study were all woman giving birth, sample size 80 respondents. Sampling technique with proportional random sampling. Hypothesis test used chi-squared test and continued multivariate analysis used binary logistic regression. A two-tailed *P*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The results of the study were associated level of education, knowledge, perception of risk factors, threat, advantages, accessibility and advice from health workers with choice of birth attendants ($p < 0.05$). But age and parity not any significant association with choice of birth attendants ($p > 0.05$). Dominant factor for with choice of birth attendants was level of education.

Conclusion: This analysis confirmed level of education was dominant factor for choice of birth attendants.

Keywords: Choice of birth attendants, Education, Woman giving birth

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program 2015-2030, Indonesia targets to be able to reduce maternal mortality to 102 / 100,000 live births and infant mortality to 23 / 100,000 live births, and coverage of deliveries assisted by health workers to 95% in 2015. [1]

Data Indonesia, many deliveries assisted by non-health workers from 34 provinces in Indonesia deliveries assisted by health workers were the highest in West Nusa Tenggara, namely 100.02% and the lowest coverage of deliveries assisted by health workers was in North Maluku Province 17.79%, for the area of West Sumatra Province the coverage of delivery assistance by health workers was 79.64%, still below the government's target of 95%. [2]

The role of traditional birth attendants is still quite high, especially in rural areas, even though every birth saves the risk of becoming an emergency, the role of health workers is needed so that labor takes place safely. One of the reasons for the still high role of shamans in Indonesia is that because of the low cost, the traditional birth attendants is considered capable of providing complete services from the time the mother is pregnant to postpartum. [1,3]

The high number of births assisted by traditional birth attendants is supported by several factors that influence changes in a person's behavior which are related to health information, social environment, social culture, and from several external and internal factors. [4]

West Sumatra Province has 18 districts and cities. The highest coverage of

childbirth assistance by health workers is in Padang Panjang City, which is 101% and the lowest coverage of delivery assistance in West Sumatra Province is in Tanah Datar District of 72%. [5]

This data shows that childbirth assistance by health workers is still far from the expected target where the target of achieving delivery assistance by health workers is for West Sumatra Province (95%). Delivery assistance assisted by health workers is reduced due to the lack of public awareness of the importance of delivery assistance by health workers in accordance with health standards. [5]

The aim of the study was to determine factors associated with choice of birth attendants in the working area of Batipuh I Primary Health Care, Tanah Data District West Sumatra Province Indonesia.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Study Design and Research Sample

The study was conducted using a cross sectional study, in the working area of Batipuh I Primary Health Care, Tanah Data District West Sumatra Province Indonesia

RESULT

from January-March 2019. The population in this study were all woman giving birth, sample size 80 respondents. Sampling technique with proportional random sampling.

Operational Definitions

The variables of this study included independent variables: age, level of education, knowledge, parity, perception of risk factors, threat, advantages, accessibility and advice from health workers and dependent variable is choice of birth attendants.

Data Collection Technique

This study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Medical Faculty, Universitas Andalas with registration number 470/KEP/FK/2018.

Data Analysis

The quantitative variables were recorded as frequency and percentage. Hypothesis test used chi-squared test and continued multivariate analysis used binary logistic regression. A two-tailed *P*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data were analyzed using the SPSS version 21.0.

Table 1: Factors associated with choice of birth attendants

Variables	Birth Attendants				Total		p value
	Not health workers		Health workers		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
Age							
Low risk	22	37.3	37	62.7	59	100	1.000
High risk	8	38.1	13	61.9	21	100	
Level of education							
Low	28	51.9	26	48.1	54	100	<0.001
High	2	7.7	24	92.3	26	100	
Level of knowledge							
Low	28	45.9	33	54.1	61	100	0.012
High	2	10.5	17	89.5	19	100	
Parity							
High	20	35.1	37	64.9	57	100	0.655
Low	10	43.5	13	56.5	23	100	
Perception of risk factors							
Negative	18	64.3	10	35.7	28	100	0.001
Positive	12	23.1	40	76.9	52	100	
Perception of threat							
Negative	19	76.0	6	24	25	100	<0.001
Positive	11	20	44	80	55	100	
Perception of advantages							
Negative	22	64.7	12	35.3	34	100	<0.001
Positive	8	17.4	38	82.6	46	100	
Accessibility							
Good	26	34.2	50	65.8	76	100	0.034
Not good	4	100	0	0	4	100	
Advice from health workers							
Good	26	34.2	50	65.8	76	100	0.034
Not good	4	100	0	0	4	100	

Factors associated with choice of birth attendants in the working area of Batipuh I Primary Health Care, Tanah Data District West Sumatera Province Indonesia (Table 1).

Table 1 known there were associated level of education, knowledge, perception of risk factors, threat, advantages, accessibility and advice from health workers with choice of birth attendants ($p < 0.05$). But age and parity not any significant association with choice of birth attendants ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2: Multivariate analysis

Variables	Sig. (2-tailed)	B	Exp (B)
Education level	0.024	2.331	10.285
Knowledge	0.050	2.593	13.375
Risk	0.007	2.146	8.550
Threat	0.315	.969	2.635
Advantages	0.150	1.333	3.792
Accessibility	0.999	-21.250	.000

Table 2 known dominant factor for with choice of birth attendants was level of education (OR 10.285).

DISCUSSION

The results of this study known there were associated level of education, knowledge, perception of risk factors, threat, advantages, accessibility and advice from health workers with choice of birth attendants. Dominant factor for with choice of birth attendants was level of education.

There are still mothers who have a high level of education but the birth is still helped by a traditional birth attendants, this can be caused by other factors such as social culture and family influence which has become a habit in the mother's family to give birth with a traditional birth attendants.

The results of this study indicate that the number of respondents found choosing birth attendants to non-health workers is one of the factors caused by the lack of knowledge held by respondents to health workers.

Parity of pregnant women is an important factor in determining the fate of the mother and fetus during pregnancy and childbirth. But in this case the multiparity or

primipara maternal parity does not influence the actions of mothers in choosing birth attendants to health workers.

The actions of individuals to seek treatment and prevent disease will be driven by the seriousness of the disease or the threat seen regarding the symptoms and diseases of individuals or the community. If a pregnant woman feels that there is a safety threat to herself and her baby, the mother will look for a health worker to help her childbirth. There are still mothers who already have a positive perception of the threat of labor with a traditional birth attendants, but it turns out that the birth is still assisted by a traditional birth attendants, this can be caused by other factors, such as encouragement from the husband and family. [6]

If a pregnant woman believes in the benefits of labor with a health worker, the mother will choose a health worker for her birth attendant even though there are obstacles she faces. The role of midwives involves providing support to women in preparation for childbirth. Related to the provision of information and care in the antenatal period, findings from qualitative studies inform that women hope to be given care and information from people they consider experts. Even though women go to relatives and friends to get all information about pregnancy and birth, this information is considered to be unreliable - less expert - than information provided by health professionals. [7,8]

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study confirmed there were associated level of education, knowledge, perception of risk factors, threat, advantages, accessibility and advice from health workers with choice of birth attendants. Dominant factor for with choice of birth attendants was level of education.

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